

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BISPHENOL F EPOXY RESIN AT DIFFERENT CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

The tensile and compressive mechanical properties of bisphenol F epoxy resin at different cryogenic temperatures (from 20°C to -180°C) were measured by experimental approaches. First, the elastic modulus of the epoxy resin at different temperatures was measured, and it was found the elastic modulus of the epoxy resin increased with the decrease of temperature. From -180°C to -120°C, the modulus is basically linear with the temperature; while in the range between -120°C and 20°C, there is an approximately quadratic relationship. Then, the strength of the epoxy resin was tested. The results indicates that both the tensile and compressive strength of the epoxy resin increases with the decrease of temperature, and the temperature's influence on compressive strength is greater than on tensile strength. Finally, the macro and micro fracture morphologies of the specimens were checked, so as to reveal the intrinsic mechanism of the epoxy resin's different mechanical behaviors at room and cryogenic temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the development of aerospace industry, the requirements of light weight for aircraft are getting higher and higher. As the main structure of the launch vehicle, the propellant tank has a large volume and a high mass proportion. In order to meet the needs of weight loss, the development of high-strength, low-density tanks have become the primary goal of the power countries in spaceflight [1-4]. High performance carbon fiber reinforced resin matrix composites have been widely used in aerospace industry due to their high specific strength, high specific modulus, low density, low thermal conductivity, corrosion resistance and fatigue resistance, and it is gradually replacing the key parts of metal materials used in the manufacture of aerospace vehicles [5-9]. It is found that, compared with aluminum lithium alloy used currently, composite materials can make the tank weight loss by 27%, insulation material weight loss by 12%, so the vehicle weight will be reduced by 7.5%, which can make the low altitude flight cost reduced by 37% [10,11].

However, the development of composite cryogenic tank needs to investigate cryogenic temperature mechanical properties of the materials in depth. In this paper, the mechanical properties of bisphenol F epoxy resin were tested under different cryogenic temperatures, to study how cryogenic temperature influences the stiffness, strength and failure behavior of bisphenol F epoxy resin, so as to provide the basis for the design of low temperature composite tank.

2 SPECIMEN PREPARATION

In order to obtain the complete mechanical performance of bisphenol F epoxy resin, both the tensile and compressive properties were investigated. The tensile and compressive test specimens were made according to the ASTM D638-99 standard, with the specific sizes of tensile specimens shown in Figure 1, and the standard size of the compressive specimens are cylinder with 10mm radius and 25mm height. The specimens were made through the following procedures: first, bisphenol F epoxy resin and the curing agent 4, 4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM) were mixed in a certain proportion and poured into the moulds. Then they were put in the oven with curing temperature 100°C for 2 hours,

130°C for 2 hours, and 160°C for 4 hours. After that, the specimens were taken out from the mould and polished with sandpaper.

In order to avoid slipping between the clamp and the sample, reinforced sheets were glued at both ends of the tensile specimens. At room temperature, aluminum reinforced sheets were used; for low temperature, three layers of glass fiber cloth were adopted. For compressive specimens, in order to ensure high perpendicularity, the two end surfaces of the specimens were milled smoothly.

Figure 1: The geometry and sizes of the tensile specimen (Unit: mm)

Figure 2: The geometry and sizes of the tensile specimen (Unit: mm)

Figure 3: The compressive mould and specimens

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The specimens were tested by the universal mechanical property testing machine, with the testing temperature controlled by the thermodynamic environment control system (as shown in Figure 4). The cryogenic temperature was obtained by the environmental insulation box which was connected to a liquid nitrogen spraying device. During the experiment, liquid nitrogen was sprayed from self pressurized liquid nitrogen tank into the environmental chamber; by controlling the amount of liquid nitrogen sprayed, different cryogenic temperatures were obtained. When the temperature was reduced to the required one, it was kept for 5 minutes, and then the experiment was carried out. For both tensile and compressive test, the loading rate was 1mm/min, and low temperature extensometer was used to measure the strain of the specimens. For each temperature, three specimens were tested.

In order to obtain the relationship between the elastic modulus and the temperature, the elastic

modulus of the specimen was measured at interval of 10°C in the range of 20°C to -180°C. During the test, the temperature was kept constant, and the specimen was loaded to 1kN and then unloaded, from which the loading and unloading stress-strain curves were obtained. When changing to the next temperature, due to the change of temperature, the specimen deformed and resulted in a residual load. To release this residual load, the load was manually set back to zero and then the next test was carried out.

In order to obtain the strength of the material, the specimen must be continually loaded until failure, which is much costly and time-consuming. Thus only five temperatures with an interval of 50°C were investigated, i.e., 20°C, -30°C, -80°C, -130°C, and -180°C.

Figure 4: Universal mechanical property testing machine for cryogenic test

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The elastic modulus, strength and elongation of bisphenol F epoxy resin were calculated according to ASTM D638-99 standard.

4.1 Elastic modulus

The elastic modulus of the material is measured by the tensile specimens. The typical loading-unloading stress-strain curves of the tensile specimens at -10°C and -180°C are shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that the loading curve and unloading curve almost coincide, which means that the specimens are in elastic state during the test, thus the measured modulus is reliable. The relationship between the modulus and temperature of the three specimens is shown in Figure 6. It can be seen that the three curves have good consistency, with the elastic modulus increases with the decreasing of temperature.

Figure 5: Loading-unloading stress-strain curves of the tensile specimen

Figure 6: The elastic modulus-temperature relationship

In order to further analyze the relationship between the elastic modulus and temperature, the average modulus of the three specimens were calculated, as listed in table 1.

Temperature (°C)	Modulus (MPa)	Temperature (°C)	Modulus (MPa)	Temperature (°C)	Modulus (MPa)
20	2873.0	-50	3667.7	-120	5613.7
10	3023.5	-60	3876.0	-130	5751.7
0	3080.0	-70	4100.0	-140	5982.0
-10	3207.3	-80	4356.3	-150	6140.7
-20	3311.0	-90	4608.3	-160	6323.7
-30	3404.7	-100	4902.0	-170	6536.3
-40	3534.7	-110	5182.7	-180	6701.3

Table 1: Elastic modulus of the epoxy resin at different temperatures

The relationship between the average modulus and temperature is illustrated in Figure 7. As can be

seen, the relationship is not completely linear. It seems that the trend changes at the temperature of about -120°C: from -180°C to -120°C, the average modulus is basically linear with the temperature, but in the range between -120°C to 20°C, there is an approximately quadratic relationship between the average modulus and the temperature. This is an interesting phenomenon, which has not been reported ever before.

Figure 7: The relationship between average modulus and temperature with fitting curves

4.2 Tensile strength and failure strain

The stress-strain curves of the tensile specimens at five different temperatures for strength test are shown in Figure 8. It is found that the bisphenol F epoxy resin shows an elastic-plastic behavior at room temperature (20°C), with an obvious yielding stage. However, it gradually becomes brittle with the decrease of temperature: the curve under -30°C and -80°C are slightly bent, shows incomplete brittleness and a little plasticity, while curves under -130°C and -180°C are basically linear, with almost no yielding stage.

Figure 8: The stress-strain curves of the tensile specimens at different temperatures

The tensile strength with error limits of the specimens at different temperatures are shown in Figure 9. It can be seen from the figure that with the decrease of temperature, the strength of epoxy resin increases gradually. The relationship between the tensile strength and temperature is not completely linear. With the decrease of temperature, the tensile strength increases slowly at first; and then it increases more rapidly when the temperature is below -80°C .

Figure 9: The tensile strength of the epoxy resin at different temperatures

The failure strain of the tensile specimens with error limits under different temperatures is shown in Figure 10. It is found that the failure strain under room temperature is much higher than that under cryogenic temperature, which is due to the fact that the material exhibits elastic-plastic at room temperature, and relatively brittle at low temperature. And the relationship between the failure strain and temperature varies: with the decrease of temperature, the failure strain declines rapidly at first, and then it gradually slows down, and finally remains almost unchanged.

Figure 10: The failure strain of the epoxy resin under different temperatures

4.3 Compressive strength

The stress-strain curves of the compressive specimens under five different temperatures are shown in Figure 11, with the nominal strain used. It can be found that, at room temperature (20°C) the epoxy

resin shows obvious yielding stage; with the decrease of temperature, the failure strain decreases, and the yielding stage gradually becomes unobvious. It can also be seen that the slope of the curve increases with the decrease of temperature, indicating that the elastic modulus of the material increases with the decrease of temperature.

Figure 11: The stress-strain curves of the compressive specimens under different temperatures

The average compressive strength of the epoxy resin with error limit under different temperatures is shown in Figure 12. It is found that, with the decrease of temperature, the compressive strength of the material increases rapidly. The compressive strength of the epoxy resin at -180°C is almost three times the strength at room temperature, compared with the ratio of about 1.7 for tensile strength.

Figure 12: The compressive strength of the epoxy resin under different temperatures

4.4 Damage morphology

In order to understand the intrinsic mechanism of the cryogenic temperature's influence on the mechanical performance of epoxy resin, the fracture section of specimens at room temperature and low temperature (-180°C) were examined and compared. As shown in Figure 13, the tensile fracture surface of the specimens is relatively rough at room temperature; while the cross-section is relatively smooth under low temperature.

Figure 13: The fracture section of tensile specimens at room temperature and low temperature (-180°C)

The specimens after compression under room temperature and low temperature are shown in Figure 14. It can be found that at room temperature there is no obvious crack inside the specimen after compression, with the ultimate failure mode like a drum which is thick in the middle and thin at both ends (Figure 14a); with the decrease of temperature, obvious cracks appear gradually, and the main performance is that the internal resin slide inducing white spot (Figure 14b); when the temperature further decreased, the resin is completely compressed into pieces, as shown in Fig. 14c. Through the comparison of the damaged pattern under room temperature and low temperature, the fact that the epoxy resin becomes brittle at low temperature is confirmed intuitively.

Figure 14: Compressive failure modes of compressive specimens at different temperatures: (a) 20 °C (b) -80 °C (c) -180 °C

To further illustrate the intrinsic mechanism of this influence, the microstructure of the specimens was examined by Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The microscopic morphology of the fracture section for the tensile and compressive specimens at room and low temperature are shown in Figure 15. By comparison it can be found that the fracture section at room temperature is relatively rough, which indicates elastic-plastic failure; while the fracture section at low temperature is relatively smooth, which represents brittle fracture.

Figure 15: The microscopic fracture morphology of tensile and compressive specimens at room temperature and low temperature

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the mechanical properties of bisphenol F epoxy resin under different low temperatures were systematically studied, with the following conclusions drawn.

(1) The elastic modulus of the epoxy resin increases with the decrease of temperature, and the relationship between the elastic modulus and temperature can be divided into two stages: from -180°C to -120°C, the modulus is basically linear with the temperature, but in the range between -120°C and 20°C, there is an approximately quadratic relationship.

(2) The tensile and compressive strength of the epoxy resin both increase with the decrease of temperature, and the temperature's influence on compressive strength is greater than on tensile strength.

(3) The mechanical behaviour of the epoxy resin at room temperature is elastic-plastic; but at cryogenic temperature, the mechanical behaviour of the epoxy resin gradually becomes brittle.

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